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A universal chemotherapeutic strategy that incorporates growth factor inhibition with traditional chemotherapy.

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GF inhibitor + K/P transducing GF signal + K/P transducing compensatory signaling + MDR pump inhibitor + reduced dose of chemotherapy (e.g., paclitaxel or doxorubicin)